

The Offloading Dilemma: Exploring the Boundaries of Programmable Data Planes

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Abstract—In-Network Computing (INC) is transforming how we design and evaluate modern networks by enabling programmable data planes to execute computational tasks at line rate. However, deciding which functions to offload, to which device and using which strategy is not a trivial task. This PhD project explores the opportunities, challenges and boundaries of offloading network functions and application logic to programmable switches and SmartNICs. Through a series of case studies, we demonstrate that INC-based solutions enhance both network efficiency and application performance. On the other hand, we also demonstrate the tradeoffs of these offloadings and how they can impact the infrastructure in terms of performance and resource utilization. Our findings provide actionable insights for the deployment of INC in real-world scenarios, highlighting where offloading delivers the most value and where traditional approaches remain preferable.

Index Terms—In-Network Computing, offloading, P4.

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demands on distributed systems, cloud platforms, and machine learning have significantly intensified the pressure placed on network infrastructure. To address requirements such as nanosecond communication delays, high-speed data handling, and detailed visibility into traffic flows, researchers and engineers have embraced the concept of programmable data planes. These systems make it possible to dynamically adapt the way packets are processed, embedding custom behaviors directly within network devices. With the support of languages like P4 [1] and the advancement of hardware architectures, such as programmable switches [2] and Smart Network Interface Cards (SmartNICs) [3]–[5], programmable data planes opened the doors for the in-network computing (INC) paradigm.

INC allows network operators to leverage the network not just for forwarding packets, but also as a computational substrate. Offloading tasks to the data plane goes beyond traditional network functions, such as load balancing [6] and filtering, to application-specific logic such as video streaming Quality of Experience (QoE) management decisions [7] or telemetry extraction [8], and can bring substantial performance benefits. It can reduce latency, free up CPU on end-hosts, reduce energy consumption, and enable faster response times for latency-sensitive services. These possibilities have inspired academic and industrial work exploring application offloading and INC as a foundation for next-generation systems.

However, the design space is far from settled. Not all computations are suitable for offloading. Data planes are con-

Fig. 1. The offloading dilemma

strained by limited memory, restricted programming models, and a tight coupling to hardware capabilities. In addition, offloading logic to the network can introduce challenges around maintainability, debugging, correctness, and interoperability. As a result, deciding what to offload, where, and how remains an open and nuanced question. The decision is not only technical but also architectural, with implications for system design, application development, and network management. Figure 1 illustrates the offloading dilemma. Modern networks offer a wide range of processing units, including programmable switches(1), SmartNICs with integrated CPUs(2), traditional CPU servers(3), and GPUs(4). Deciding where to implement application tasks, network functions, monitoring mechanisms, or even machine learning algorithms is often non-trivial, as each device presents different capabilities and trade-offs.

In this PhD project, we are looking to analyze the boundaries of data plane offloading. It aims to analyze the opportunities and limitations of offloading both application logic and network functions to programmable data planes. The research investigates the trade-offs involved in offloading decisions by selecting multiple use cases for offloading, and analyzing the implications for performance, resource utilization, reliability, power consumption, and others relevant metrics for each use case. Furthermore, benefiting from the performance and flexibility provided by INC, we also explore the development of tools required to support efficient experimentation in these programmable networking environments. To this end, we develop network emulators and traffic generators based on programmable switches and SmartNICs, designed to provide

realistic, flexible, and high-performance representations of programmable environments. These tools facilitate and improve the evaluation of new in-network solutions.

By rethinking how and when to leverage the network as a computational resource, this work contributes to a deeper understanding of offloading as a first-class design concern in modern networked systems. The goal is to provide concrete insights and empirical evidence to guide system architects, researchers, and practitioners in evaluating the trade-offs associated with offloading strategies, while also identifying opportunities for new abstractions, tools, and design methodologies that better align application demands with programmable infrastructure capabilities.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Next, we provide key background concepts and the fundamental challenges involved in this research. Then, we present our research questions, and the expected contributions.

A. In-Network Computing

INC represents a fundamental shift in how we approach computation, moving processing tasks directly into the network data plane. Thanks to programmable hardware like P4-enabled switches and SmartNICs, we can now implement custom packet processing that far exceeds simple forwarding, think real-time telemetry, adaptive load balancing, and even distributed consensus mechanisms, all operating at line rate.

Three key benefits make INC so compelling: reduced latency from moving computation closer to data, significant relief for overloaded servers, and unprecedented real-time network visibility. However, these programmable platforms come with hard constraints, limited memory, restricted control flow, and computational boundaries, that force us to rethink traditional approaches. This tradeoff between potential and limitation is exactly what makes INC so explored in the literature, as we work to determine what computations belong in the network and how to best integrate them.

B. Offloading in Modern Networked Systems

Offloading has long been employed as a strategy to improve performance, efficiency, and scalability in computing systems. Traditionally, it has taken the form of shifting tasks from general-purpose CPUs to more specialized processing units, such as GPUs or hardware accelerators. In networking, offloading has historically occurred at the transport and application layers, such as TCP Segmentation Offload (TSO), Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA), or kernel bypass techniques. As data rates and application demands increase, the scope of offloading is expanding to include the network fabric itself.

Programmable data planes are redefining what is possible. Suddenly, network devices are not just moving packets, they are executing application logic. This promises huge leaps in performance and visibility, but it also forces us to confront fundamental questions: How should applications and networks

communicate when the boundary between them blurs? Traditional models treat the network as a passive black box, but offloading turns it into an active computational partner. That shift demands new approaches to interfaces, trust models, and coordination, challenging decades-old assumptions

Resource constraints. Programmable data planes face inherent limitations in computation and memory. Designed for throughput-optimized packet processing rather than general-purpose computing, these devices impose strict constraints on instruction sets, memory access, and control flow. This forces developers to simplify or re-architect algorithms, creating a tension between functionality and feasibility that demands better tooling and abstractions.

Network heterogeneity. The diversity of hardware platforms, from ASIC switches to FPGA NICs, each with unique capabilities and tool chains, complicates portable offloading development. Code rarely transfers directly between targets, hindering experimentation and requiring significant reimplementations. This fragmentation underscores the need for standardization or robust translation layers across platforms.

Performance requirements. While data plane offloading promises low latency and high throughput, the strict real-time processing budgets constrain functionality. Every operation must complete within fixed packet-time windows, eliminating moderately complex logic. Also, in some architectures, depending on the algorithm executed, performance may degrade significantly. This demands careful optimization and benchmarking to verify actual performance gains.

Limited stateful capabilities. Stateful processing faces particular challenges due to constrained memory architectures and lock-free access requirements. Many useful network functions require state tracking, but current hardware often forces approximations like sketches, limiting dynamic behaviors. Better state management abstractions could unlock more sophisticated functionality.

C. Research questions

Next, we present the research questions that we hope to answer at the end of the PhD project.

- **RQ1:** *What classes of applications and network functions benefit most from offloading into the data plane, and under which conditions?*
- **RQ2:** *How do hardware constraints (e.g., memory, stateful processing, pipeline depth) affect the feasibility and accuracy of offloaded logic?*
- **RQ3:** *What models of coordination and state management are needed to support complex offloaded behaviors across distributed programmable elements?*
- **RQ4:** *How the offloading of network functions and application logic to the data plane impact performance, scalability, and interoperability in heterogeneous environments?*
- **RQ5:** *Can INC-based tools support the development, testing, and deployment of offloaded applications across heterogeneous programmable platforms?*

D. Expected contributions

This research aims to advance the understanding and practice of offloading in programmable data planes by providing a structured analysis of its benefits, limitations, and deployment models. By combining empirical evaluation, tool development, and system design, this work intends to contribute with both conceptual insights and practical solutions.

First, the project will offer a taxonomy and characterization of offloadable logic, identifying which classes of applications and network functions benefit most from in-network execution and under which system or workload conditions. This will help system architects and developers make informed decisions about what to offload and when. Second, the research will explore the implications of hardware constraints, including limited memory, constrained processing logic, and shallow pipeline architectures, on the feasibility, expressiveness, and accuracy of offloaded programs. These findings will inform the design of future hardware and programming abstractions.

Third, the project will propose and evaluate models for coordination and state management in distributed programmable environments, addressing how stateful or collaborative behaviors can be safely and efficiently implemented across network elements. Fourth, it will assess the impact of offloading on key system properties, including performance, scalability, and interoperability in heterogeneous networks. Finally, the research will contribute the design and implementation of INC-based tools, such as emulators and traffic generators, that support development, experimentation, and validation of offloaded logic. These tools aim to accelerate research and development across diverse programmable platforms, easing the barrier to entry and promoting reproducibility.

III. EXPLORED USE CASES

Starting the studies on offloading, we started by investigating three different use cases: one related to networking, another to monitoring, and another to application tasks. For this purpose, we chose the use cases of link failure recovery, Quality of Experience (QoE) monitoring of video streaming sections, and collision avoidance for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). These use cases were selected because they can represent tasks that can be offloaded to the data plane, but have completely different purposes, and therefore can provide valuable insights into the benefits and boundaries of INC.

A. Fast Reroute for recovery from link failures

Fast recovery from link failures is essential in modern data center networks, which are characterized by high-throughput demands and stringent availability requirements. Traditional failure recovery mechanisms, especially those that rely on control-plane reconfigurations, often suffer from unacceptable latency, potentially leading to packet loss and service degradation. Even when implemented in programmable data planes, many existing Fast Reroute (FRR) mechanisms redirect all affected traffic to a single backup path, ignoring the Equal-Cost Multi Path (ECMP) nature of traffic distribution. This results in imbalanced load, congestion on backup links, and

Fig. 2. RESISTING overview

reduced overall resilience, particularly in the presence of multiple simultaneous failures.

To address these limitations, we contributed to the development of RESISTING [9], a novel FRR mechanism integrated with ECMP and implemented entirely in the data plane using P4. Figure 2 presents an overview of the proposed strategy. The key idea is to perform failure-aware port reordering and path recalculation on the fly, allowing affected traffic to be redistributed evenly across the remaining operational paths in the ECMP group. RESISTING introduces lightweight control logic for temporary recirculation and uses data-plane registers to dynamically update the set of available paths, all while avoiding central coordination. We developed implementations for both BMv2 and Tofino switches, carefully adapting to the architectural constraints of each platform.

Our experiments show that RESISTING significantly improves resilience under failure scenarios compared to state-of-the-art approaches like PURR [10]. In simulated and real environments, RESISTING maintained 100% traffic delivery even under three simultaneous link failures, while PURR experienced up to 14% packet loss due to load imbalance. Moreover, RESISTING’s P4 implementation consumed less than 30% of Tofino pipeline resources, leaving room for integration with other in-network functions. These results highlight RESISTING’s practicality and effectiveness in improving failure recovery for load-balanced programmable networks.

B. In-network QoE management

Delivering high-quality video streaming, especially immersive applications like 360-degree Virtual Reality (VR), is increasingly challenging due to the demanding performance requirements of low-latency, high-throughput networks. Traditional QoE estimation and optimization approaches are often implemented in the control plane or at the end-user player. While accurate, these methods suffer from delayed reactions to network issues, particularly when they require communication with the data plane, which can take tens of milliseconds, far exceeding the latency budget of modern applications. In applications like VR and XR, even small delays (e.g., 5–10 ms) can significantly degrade user experience. This motivates a shift toward in-network QoE (INQoE) management, where estimation and optimization occur directly within programmable switches and SmartNICs, offering real-time adaptation and tighter control.

In [7], [11], we propose the first fully data-plane strategy that both estimates and improves QoE for video streaming applications, without any intervention from the control plane.

Fig. 3. InQoE management

The strategy relies on packet-level telemetry and uses the Inter-Packet Gap (IPG) as the core metric to infer QoE. This metric is lightweight, hardware-friendly, and well-suited for implementation on P4-based switches. Figure 3 illustrates how our strategy works. Using a 5-tuple flow classifier and an Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) over IPG values, our system dynamically identifies performance degradation. When degradation is detected (i.e., IPGw crosses a predefined threshold), the system autonomously applies queue management policies, such as traffic prioritization, entirely within the switch. This combined monitoring and mitigation approach enables proactive and localized responses to network conditions without waiting for control plane decisions, significantly reducing reaction times.

We implemented our strategy on a commercial programmable switch and evaluated it using a realistic 360-degree VR streaming setup. During congestion scenarios, flows optimized by our approach maintained a regular IPGw and achieved up to 6 Mbps throughput, compared to less than 2 Mbps for unmonitored flows. The corresponding QoE, measured as Mean Opinion Score (MOS), was 4.8 for the optimized flow and only 2.3 for the standard flow (on a scale from 0 to 5). These results validate that QoE-aware decisions can be taken entirely in the data plane and highlight the potential of INQoE to meet the demands of next-generation immersive video applications.

C. Collision avoidance for UAVs

The rise of next-generation networks and the widespread adoption of UAVs across sectors like agriculture, logistics, and public safety have pushed the boundaries of existing network infrastructure. One of the most critical challenges in UAV deployment is real-time collision avoidance, a safety requirement that becomes increasingly difficult to satisfy in dense or latency-sensitive environments. Conventional approaches rely heavily on centralized processing (e.g., cloud or MEC-based APIs), which are often hindered by end-to-end latencies introduced by multiple network layers and processing nodes. Even in a 5G network, where access delays can be minimal, cumulative processing across the stack (application layer, MEC, OS) can reach several milliseconds, enough to degrade response time in high-speed or safety-critical UAV operations. These constraints call for a new paradigm where decisions are made within the network, bypassing traditional vertical processing bottlenecks.

Fig. 4. In-network UAV collision avoidance strategy

To address these limitations, we contributed to developing an in-network collision avoidance mechanism built entirely within the data plane using P4 programmable switches [12] (See figure 4). Unlike prior work, which only offloaded basic tasks to the network, our approach directly embeds geometric collision avoidance logic—based on the 3DVFH+ algorithm, into the switch pipeline. This enables real-time decision-making at the edge, where critical information about UAV positions is processed without leaving the network device.

The core of the implementation lies in representing the 3D environment as a histogram-based spatial map inside the switch registers, which is updated dynamically as UAVs transmit position updates. The switch parses custom UAV-specific headers, detects potential collisions based on proximity zones (warning, detection, collision), and proactively modifies or mirrors packets to redirect UAVs with new trajectories. We built this on a Tofino switch using the P4 language and validated it through emulated 5G environments with realistic latency, link metrics, and UAV behaviors, integrated with CoppeliaSim. Our evaluation demonstrates that in-network processing delivers significantly faster and more reliable collision avoidance than traditional remote API methods. Even under varying latency conditions (5ms to 120ms), the P4-based in-network system consistently avoided collisions by reacting within microseconds, well before the remote API could respond. The system proved resilient across multiple UAV speeds (up to 8 m/s), and its decision-making remained consistent regardless of traffic delays. Additionally, our implementation showed efficient hardware resource usage, using only a small fraction of available Tofino pipeline resources, making it a scalable solution for larger UAV swarms.

IV. ENVISIONED USE CASES

Next, we describe the next steps of our research, which involve new use cases and techniques to optimize offloading. **Server and application level telemetry.** We are developing a standardized method for servers and applications to communicate operational state to network devices. This work [13] builds on our earlier investigations into distributed agent architectures, where lightweight components deployed across servers, SmartNICs, and switches exchange structured synchronization messages. Such a framework would fundamentally expand the visibility available to in-network applications, for the first time, they could incorporate server-level metrics (e.g., CPU

utilization, application requirements) into forwarding decisions. This capability opens new possibilities for intelligent offloading to programmable data planes, though it requires careful design tradeoffs between synchronization overhead. Our current efforts focus on system design and evaluation of the overheads in realistic deployment scenarios.

Virtual network functions offloading. In [14] we explore the potential for offloading Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) workloads to SmartNICs. Given how extensively VNFs are deployed in modern data centers, we hypothesize that partial offloading could yield several key benefits: freeing valuable CPU cores, reducing processing latency and power consumption, and increasing overall system throughput through parallel execution on both host processors and SmartNIC hardware. Early experiments focus on identifying which are VNFs offloading limits for the Bluefield-2 SmartNIC, understanding principally the performance boundaries.

CU-UP offloading. We are currently investigating whether we can offload core Control Unit - User Plane (CU-UP) functions in O-RAN systems to SmartNICs and programmable switches. Since the CU-UP handles most of the grunt work for user data traffic, moving some of this processing to specialized hardware could give us two potential wins: lower latency and reduced server CPU overhead. We are investigating the trade-offs of this offloading by methodically testing how this plays out in practice. We are looking at the performance, how well it scales, and whether it meshes with the other RAN components.

Once we complete all planned use cases and analyze the tradeoffs involved in offloading various applications to different network components, our next step will be to create an automated offloading strategy. This system would intelligently distribute workloads based on multiple optimization targets, such as performance, latency reduction, energy efficiency, etc.

V. NETWORK TESTING MEETS PROGRAMMABLE HW

Network testing is another fundamental contribution of our work. By developing high-performance, high-fidelity, and flexible tools for experimentation in programmable networks, we contribute not only to improving the quality of our own experiments, but also to enabling other researchers to create more complex scenarios in their experiments. Moreover, our tools significantly improve the reproducibility of state-of-the-art solutions: approaches originally developed in large-scale, production environments (e.g., by companies testing in their enterprise data centers) can now be reproduced in smaller, more accessible setups (e.g., a single switch and a SmartNIC).

To make this possible, we have advanced on two main fronts: network topology emulation and traffic generation for different workloads. Network topology emulation aims to replicate multiple programmable network devices using just a single physical device. This approach preserves the advantages of real-world experimentation, such as high fidelity and performance, while incorporating the flexibility of software-based emulation, like scalable topology creation and configurable network metrics. For traffic generation, our objective is to support high-performance workload reproduction (e.g., generating

Fig. 5. Network testing framework

terabits-per-second traffic) while accurately modeling diverse application behaviors. In the following sections, we detail our current solutions and outline potential future use cases.

Network emulation. We present P7: the P4 Programmable Patch Panel [15], [16], a high-performance network emulator built on the Tofino ASIC. P7 enables the emulation of multiple interconnected switches with high-speed links (up to 100Gbps), complete with configurable link metrics, including latency, jitter, and packet loss. Crucially, P7 allows each emulated switch to execute custom P4 programs with unrestricted access to hardware resources (e.g., tables, registers). To extend its applicability, we are currently porting P7 to SmartNICs, enabling topology emulation beyond Tofino-based platforms.

Traffic Generation. Our work in traffic generation focuses on developing solutions that combine high-throughput capabilities (reaching terabits per second) with faithful reproduction of real network workloads. This dual approach enables rigorous evaluation of both programmable and conventional network architectures. Leveraging Tofino’s native capabilities, we have developed three complementary traffic generation systems: PIPO-TG [17], P4R [18], and TFTG [19]. These systems collectively support terabit-scale traffic generation with fully configurable flow parameters, including user-defined protocol implementations. Furthermore, they enable advanced network testing scenarios through stateful connection emulation, precise PCAP replay functionality, and deterministic nanosecond-scale delays - particularly valuable for latency-sensitive applications. For the next steps, we are extending our functionalities to also support protocols such as RDMA, and workloads such as Large-Language Models (LLMs) training in data centers.

Figure 5 presents the overarching architecture of our integrated network testing framework. The system combines traffic generation capabilities using Tofino ASICs with topology emulation spanning both programmable switches and SmartNICs. This unified environment enables simultaneous high-performance traffic generation and flexible network emulation within a single experimental setup. Through this integrated framework, we aim to advance network experimentation capabilities in two key dimensions: (1) enhancing the precision and reproducibility of our own research, and (2) providing the research community with tools to construct more robust and flexible experimental testbeds. This dual contribution addresses critical gaps in current network evaluation methodologies by enabling both high-fidelity emulation and realistic traffic generation within a unified environment.

VI. PRELIMINARY INSIGHTS

Based on the research questions presented in Section II-C, and the work developed so far, we present some initial insights based on the use cases implemented.

RQ1: Our initial observations reveal that network functions generally present the most straightforward offloading opportunities, delivering immediate performance improvements with relatively simple implementations. For instance, offloading [9] demonstrates how even basic optimizations can significantly enhance throughput for all traversing traffic. Application-specific tasks, as explored in [7] and [12], show more constrained benefits. While they can be efficient, their specialized nature limits broader applicability. For example, the same threshold strategy effective for [7] fails to consistently optimize QoE in other video streaming applications. This suggests the need for protocol-aware adaptation, where parameters like the IPGW threshold must be carefully tuned based on application characteristics and traffic patterns.

RQ2: Our implementation strategies reveal how architectural constraints distinctly impact offloading decisions across different targets. Programmable switches maintain line-rate performance but impose strict limitations on pipeline stages and instruction sets. SmartNICs offer greater programming flexibility, but at the cost of reduced throughput. This fundamental trade-off between expressiveness and performance underscores the importance of carefully evaluating architectural capabilities when deciding where to offload specific functions.

RQ3: Based on insights from the literature, we are designing a novel state sharing model to systematically evaluate its impact on our target use cases. This approach will allow us to quantify how enhanced visibility across the system stack influences both offloading decisions and overall performance.

RQ4: Programmable switches typically maintain line-rate performance unless employing costly operations like recirculation. However, as demonstrated in [14], alternative architectures often suffer severe performance degradation when offloading, in some cases operating below 10% of their total capacity. Currently, our work focuses exclusively on centralized strategies; distributed approaches remain unexplored and present an important area for future investigation.

RQ5: INC has emerged as the state-of-the-art approach for network testing. Our works [15]–[19] demonstrate how programmable data planes enable novel testing tools that achieve an unprecedented balance between flexibility and performance. These solutions combine the programmability of software-based approaches with the ability to generate multi-terabit traffic loads (Tbps), overcoming traditional tradeoffs between fidelity and scale in network experimentation.

VII. FINAL REMARKS

In this work, we presented the current status of the Francisco's PhD. project. This PhD project seeks to characterize the fundamental limits and practical tradeoffs of offloading computational tasks to programmable data planes. Early results from our initial use cases demonstrate measurable benefits not

just for traditional network functions, but also for broader compute offloading scenarios. Building on these findings, we will systematically evaluate additional applications to offload, and develop a comprehensive framework for offloading decisions. Finally, this work aims to provide actionable insights into when and how to leverage programmable hardware effectively, clarifying both its capabilities and constraints.

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